

Soil and crop management

Effect of nitrogen levels and application time on direct-sown rice

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Direct sown Kranti (1981) and Ratna (1982) were tested for response to 20, 40, 60, or 80 kg N/ha applied at sowing, interculture by country plow, tillering, or panicle initiation at Sarkanda Farm, Bilaspur. Soil was a sandy loam with

180-87-436 kg available NPK/ha in 1981 and 100-65-622 kg available NPK/ha in 1982.

Drought limited response to fertilizer in 1981, but different N application levels significantly affected number of tillers/plant, panicle length, and filled spikelets for Kranti. N application did not significantly affect those characters for Ratna. Application of 80 kg N/ha increased yield significantly over that of other treatments, which yielded similarly (see table).

Applications of N at sowing, interculture, or as four splits (sowing, intercul-

ture, tillering, and panicle initiation) produced similar results. Application of N in equal splits at sowing and interculture, interculture and tillering, and ½ at interculture and equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation produced similarly and yielded significantly more tillers than other treatments (see table). Grain yield was significantly more when N was applied at interculture, tillering, and panicle initiation.

Yields tended to be low because incidence of gall midge, bacterial blight, and sheath rot was high. □

Effect of nitrogen levels and application time on yield-contributing characters and rice yield, Bilaspur, India.

Treatment	Kranti, 1981				Ratna, 1982			
	Effective tillers (no./plant)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Effective tillers (no./plant)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Nitrogen (kg/ha)</i>								
20	2.3	20	14	3.1	2.2	20	22	2.2
40	2.6	21	13	3.2	2.4	21	17	2.4
60	2.7	20	10	3.2	2.4	20	22	2.4
80	2.8	21	9	3.4	2.7	22	17	2.8
CD (0.05)	0.2	1	2	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.3
<i>Application time</i>								
At sowing	2.4	20	11	2.9	2.2	21	16	2.0
At interculture	2.5	20	11	3.2	2.4	21	23	2.5
Equal splits at sowing and interculture	2.8	20	10	3.2	2.5	20	17	2.4
Equal splits at interculture and tillering	2.7	20	12	3.3	2.4	21	24	2.5
½ N at interculture, ¼ at tillering, and ¼ at panicle initiation	2.7	21	12	3.5	2.5	21	20	2.8
Equal splits at sowing, interculture, tillering, and panicle initiation	2.4	21	12	3.2	2.3	21	16	2.6
CD (0.05)	0.3	ns	ns	ns	ns	1	5	0.3

^a ns = nonsignificant.

Paddy and air-breathing-fish culture: effects of supplemental feed on the growth and yield of rice and fish

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We studied the effects of supplemental feed on growth and yield of mixed

cultures of two air-breathing catfishes Singhi (*Hereropnaustes fossilis*) and Magur (*Clarias batrachus*) and scented rice variety Randhunipagal at ORP in aman season.

The experiment consisted of these treatments: 1) control (rice plots without fish), 2) rice plot with fish, and 3) rice plot with fish and artificial feed.

Equal numbers of Magur and Singhi fingerlings were stocked at 1 fish/m² in early Oct. Before stocking, they were

treated with a 100 ppm solution of formalin for 30 s. Each morning, fish in treatment 3 were fed a low-cost 1:2 mixture of fishmeal and rice bran mixed with cow dung at 5% total body weight. Fish were harvested by draining the plots in mid-Nov.

Plots were 24 × 6 m with a shallow 75 × 40-cm perimeter canal. A trapezoidal protective dike bounded the canal.

Rice was sown on 10 Jul (midmonsoon). Seedlings were transplanted in wet

soil in early Aug after plots were thoroughly puddled. Rice was harvested in early Dec.

Growth and development of rice and fish with and without supplemental feed at the Operational Research Project, Pandua, West Bengal, India.

Character	Without fish		With fish
	Control	Without feed	With feed
<i>Randhunipagal</i>			
Plant height (cm)	136	134	127
Effective tillers/plant	14	10	11
Panicle length (cm)	21	21	21
Grains/panicle	106	106	121
Grain sterility (%)	11	10	10
<i>Singhi and Magur</i>			
Survival (%)	–	75	72
Increase in length (mm)	–	6	25
Increase in weight (g)	–	17	41

Releasing air-breathing fingerlings in the paddy field.

Soil was a clay loam with pH from 5.9 to 6.2. Farmyard manure at 9 t/ha was applied to all plots. Two plants spaced 20 × 20 cm were transplanted in each hill. Normal cultivation methods were practiced and water level was maintained at 8-10 cm.

Ten plants for analysis were randomly selected from each treatment and uprooted at harvest. Growth and yield data for 10 randomly selected fishes from each of treatments 2 and 3 also were recorded at harvest (see table, figure).

Rice grown with the air-breathing fish yielded more than the control, and the plots with supplemental feed produced more (see table). Plots with supplemental feed also yielded the heaviest and longest fish. Straw yield was lower in treatments 2 and 3 because of reduced plant height. □

Effect of sowing date on growth and performance of six rice varieties in western Turkey

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We studied the effect of different sowing dates on duration and yield of rice varieties and the efficacy of rice as a 2d crop after wheat or barley. Six rice varieties were sown on 7 dates at 10-d intervals from 2 Apr to 1 Jun in 1980 and 1981 in Izmir. Seedlings were transplanted at 4-

or 5-leaf stage at 10- × 30-cm spacing in 3 replications.

The highest average grain yield (8.2 t/ha) was from the second sowing, and the lowest (5.4 t/ha) was from the last sowing (see table). Calrose gave the highest average yield (9.1 t/ha) and Labelle yielded lowest (5.1 t/ha). The first seeding had the longest average duration (134 d) and the 6th seeding had the shortest (95 d). Labelle had the longest duration (121 d) and Krasnodorsky was earliest (98 d). There was a significant sowing date × variety effect on yield and duration (see table).

We concluded that in western Turkey,

- early seeding produces higher grain yield,
- short-grained Calrose and high quality varieties Kashmir Basmati and Labelle will grow and yield well if seeded in Apr,
- second crop transplanted rice (after 15 Jun) is possible after wheat or barley,
- delayed sowing generally decreases yield, and
- late sowing reduces grain yield more for short-duration varieties (Krasnodorsky and Maratelli) than for medium-duration varieties (Gritna). □

Effect of sowing date on days to heading (DH) and yield (Y) of six rices in western Turkey.

Sowing date ^a	Kashmir Basmati		Calrose		Gritna		Krasnodorsky		Labelle		Maratelli		Av	
	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH
1	8.7	138	11.4	147	6.0	127	6.3	122	6.4	141	5.8	126	7.4	134
2	9.1	128	13.0	137	6.2	116	7.2	110	6.2	130	7.4	113	8.2	122
3	7.3	120	8.7	127	5.8	109	5.8	102	5.2	126	6.7	105	6.6	115
4	7.5	113	8.6	119	5.3	101	5.4	95	5.0	121	6.2	98	6.3	108
5	8.0	105	8.6	111	5.9	94	5.4	86	4.9	113	6.2	92	6.5	100
6	6.5	98	7.5	102	5.3	91	4.5	84	4.3	107	4.8	88	5.5	95
7	6.2	101	6.0	97	6.0	100	5.0	87	3.9	107	5.2	86	5.4	96
Av	7.6	115	9.1	120	5.8	106	5.7	98	5.1	121	6.0	101		

LSD: (5%) Yield: Variety: 1.7 Sowing date: 1.7
DH: " : 4.3 " : 4.5

^a 2 Apr to 1 Jun at 10-d intervals.